

Writing with AI: EFL Students' Perceptions of ChatGPT's Role in English Writing

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Abstract: With the rapid integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into educational contexts, tools like ChatGPT have garnered attention for their potential to support writing in English as a foreign language (EFL) contexts. This study investigates university EFL learners' perceptions of ChatGPT in academic writing using a mixed-methods research design comprising a questionnaire and interviews. Results suggest that students are highly receptive to ChatGPT as a resource, due to its availability, instant support, and ease of use. Participants reported improvements in grammar, vocabulary, and text organization, along with increased confidence and reduced writing anxiety. These benefits led to increased independent, continuous participation in writing activities. There is also concern over excessive reliance on the tool, declines in critical thinking, and disquiet over the ethical implications of AI-assisted writing. Some students felt that ChatGPT was neither contextually appropriate nor trustworthy for specific questions, and they sought more explicit guidance from their institution on the responsible use of AI tools. The study suggests that ChatGPT provides meaningful assistance in enhancing EFL writing, but its integration needs to be well-managed. The focus of education should be on ethical awareness, critical engagement, and reflective learning, so that AI serves as a pedagogical scaffold rather than a substitute for independent thinking.

Anahtar Sözcükler:

Akademik dürüstlük
Eğitimde yapay zekâ
ChatGPT
Yabancı dil olarak
İngilizce yazımı
Öğrenen algıları

Yapay Zekâ ile Yazma: Yabancı Dil Öğrencilerinin İngilizce Yazmada ChatGPT'nin Rolüne İlişkin Algıları

Özet: Yapay zekânın (YZ) eğitim bağlamlarına hızla entegre edilmesiyle birlikte, ChatGPT gibi araçlar İngilizceyi yabancı dil olarak öğrenenler için yazma becerilerini destekleme potansiyelleri nedeniyle dikkat çekmektedir. Bu çalışma, üniversite düzeyindeki EFL öğrencilerinin akademik yazımda ChatGPT'ye yönelik algılarını, anket ve mülakatlardan oluşan karma yöntemli bir araştırma tasarımıyla incelemektedir. Bulgular, öğrencilerin ChatGPT'yi erişilebilirliği, anlık destek sunması ve kullanım kolaylığı nedeniyle oldukça olumlu karşıladıklarını göstermektedir. Dilbilgisi, kelime bilgisi ve metin organizasyonunda anlamlı gelişmeler gözlemlenmiş; ayrıca yazma özgüveninde artış ve yazma kaygısında azalma tespit edilmiştir. Bu kazanımlar, öğrencilerin yazma etkinliklerine daha bağımsız ve sürekli katılım göstermelerini teşvik etmiştir. Bununla birlikte, araca aşırı bağımlılık, eleştirel düşünmede olası gerilemeler ve yapay zekâ destekli yazımın etik boyutlarına ilişkin kaygılar da dile getirilmiştir. Bazı öğrenciler, ChatGPT'nin belirli sorular için bağlamsal olarak uygun ya da güvenilir olmadığını düşünmüş ve kurumlarından yapay zekâ araçlarının sorumlu kullanımına yönelik daha açık rehberlik talep etmiştir. Çalışma, ChatGPT'nin EFL yazım becerilerinin geliştirilmesinde anlamlı katkılar sunduğunu, ancak entegrasyonunun dikkatli bir şekilde yönetilmesi gerektiğini ortaya koymaktadır. Eğitimde odak noktası; etik farkındalık, eleştirel etkileşim ve yansıtıcı öğrenme olmalı, böylece yapay zekâ bağımsız düşünmenin yerini alan bir unsur değil, pedagojik bir destek aracı olarak işlev görmelidir.

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1. Introduction

The incorporation of AI into education has changed how students study, practice, and interact with academic material. In the field of EFL writing, AI-based tools like ChatGPT are gaining popularity for their potential to help learners acquire language skills, structure ideas, and receive immediate feedback. Writing, as one of the most cognitively intensive language skills, presents many EFL students with difficulties in generating content, organizing ideas, and ensuring accuracy in formal language. AI tools promise to help with these challenges. ChatGPT, created by OpenAI, is a conversational agent that can, for example, generate human-like responses, make corrections, or suggest word meanings. For many EFL students, particularly those with limited opportunities for immediate teacher support, ChatGPT is an accessible and interactive tool that helps them draft, revise, and refine their writing. Its instant, non-judgmental response can have a calming effect, helping to build a more positive attitude toward independent writing activities. However, these benefits come with pedagogical and ethical concerns, including students' blind dependence on AI, the reliability of its recommendations, and issues of academic integrity.

There have been some early studies on ChatGPT with language learning. Studies have shown that AI applications can help strengthen learner autonomy, motivation to write, and language accuracy (Mun, 2024). Nonetheless, there is still a need to explore how students feel about and utilize these tools in their daily educational lives in EFL scenarios, where writing instruction is often time-bound and dictated by curriculum requirements and large class sizes. More importantly, there is scant empirical data on EFL learners in non-native English-speaking settings, as well as their perceptions of the utility and limitations of ChatGPT in academic writing. To bridge this research gap, the present study explores EFL students' perceptions of ChatGPT as a writing aid in a Vietnamese university. By triangulating quantitative survey data with the qualitative nature of their interview responses, the study aims to uncover why learners use ChatGPT, the perceived affordances it offers for their writing practices, and the expectations or fears associated with its use. The results aim to generate more nuanced understandings of how such tools can be responsibly and effectively incorporated into EFL writing instruction, while promoting pedagogical agendas and learner development in the AI-enhanced era of education.

2. Literature Review

2.1. AI in Language Education

AI is the ability of computer systems to simulate human cognitive functions, including problem-solving, learning, reasoning, and language understanding (Russell & Norvig, 2021). AI has been gaining popularity in education to support and personalize learning, provide direct real-time instruction, and foster self-directed learning (Luckin et al., 2016). In language education, AI refers to a wide range of tools, including automated writing evaluation, intelligent tutoring systems, speech recognition, and conversational agents. AI in language learning leverages cutting-edge features of natural language processing (NLP), machine learning, and adaptive learning models, thereby representing a disruptive innovation in the classroom (Chen, 2023; Pokrivčáková, 2019). They also enhance language learning and writing skills, and help students and teachers navigate second- and foreign-language instruction more effectively (Alharbi, 2023; Lee, 2024).

Over the last decade, AI-supported writing tools for language learning have significantly transformed the landscape of second-language (L2) instruction. The rudimentary tools, such as grammar checkers and automated essay-scoring software, were followed by more advanced systems that can deliver context-specific feedback, enhance metalinguistic

sensitivity, and improve motivation to write. More recently, large language models, such as ChatGPT and Google Bard, have begun to offer interactive and generative writing assistance that approximates human feedback for polishing grammar, structure, and style (Duncanson, 2024; Lee, 2024; Pan, 2024). These instruments go beyond static corrections to encourage writing through a collaborative strategy and, when applicable, provide dynamic feedback to individual learners (Roa & Halim, 2024).

Furthermore, in the field of EFL instruction, the study of AI tools such as ChatGPT is highly relevant. EFL students commonly encounter issues with language proficiency, organization, and expression that AI can help scaffold (Song & Song, 2023; Wang, 2024). Notably, ChatGPT has demonstrated promise in enhancing students' writing fluency through immediate, personalized feedback while also promoting learner autonomy, motivation, and engagement (Pan, 2024). These applications, by providing an intelligent conversational partner or tutor, also allow learners to experiment with new linguistic forms and work through their writing at their own pace, without the typical classroom environment. This is further supported by recent empirical studies demonstrating that ChatGPT enhances learners' confidence, engagement, and self-directed learning in EFL contexts, particularly in speaking (Yıldız, 2024), and facilitates writing development through AI-assisted feedback and form-focused instruction (Grab, 2025).

However, incorporating AI into writing instruction also raises significant pedagogical and ethical concerns. As students increasingly seek AI support for writing, educators confront issues related to academic misconduct, dependence on the technology, and the fostering of critical writing skills (Duncanson, 2024). Thus, recognizing students' perceptions and experiences with AI tools is crucial for developing effective pedagogical interventions and ensuring that these technologies serve to complement, rather than replace, authentic language learning (Koka et al., 2023; Mudawy & Mohammed, 2024). AI is indeed revolutionizing language instruction, particularly in writing. Its ability to provide immediate, individualized, and context-based responses is a powerful tool for EFL students. It, however, requires careful implementation and further development to optimize its pedagogical use in a changing landscape. The growing prominence of AI tutors, such as ChatGPT, underscores the need to consider their potential implications for learner engagement, writing acquisition, and the future of language learning.

2.2. Theoretical Frameworks

This study is based on two primary theories to investigate the integration of ChatGPT in EFL writing instruction: Sociocultural Theory (SCT) and the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM).

2.2.1. Sociocultural Theory (Vygotsky)

Vygotsky's SCT (1978) emphasizes that social interaction and cultural artifacts play a critical role in the development of higher-order cognitive behavior. Crucial constructs of the theory, such as mediation, scaffolding, and ZPD (Zone of Proximal Development), for example, underscore learning in situ, guided by interaction with more knowledgeable others and the use of symbolic and technological tools (Biermann et al., 2022; Lantolf & Thorne, 2006). Tools, including language and digital technologies, operate as mediators, influencing the nature of learners' interactions with content and activities, as well as their processes of making sense of it. In this light, AI-driven writing tools such as ChatGPT may be seen as mediating artifacts that help learners traverse their ZPD by providing the scaffolding they need to complete writing tasks that are just beyond their current capacity. These tools provide dynamic scaffolding to suggest vocabulary, correct grammar, model sentence structures, and organize text, thereby taking on the role previously filled by teachers or peers in a face-to-

face environment (Athanasopoulos et al., 2023). These affordances are especially useful in an EFL context when it is difficult for teachers to give individual attention to weak learners because they are dealing with teachers with limited time to do so (larger class sizes).

Additionally, AI-enhanced writing support aligns with the trend towards dialogical interaction, which emphasizes dialogue (sociocultural). Resources such as ChatGPT enable purposeful exchanges that foster learner engagement, allowing students to actively create language through prompts that encourage them to ask questions, make suggestions, and request clarification. Such human-AI interactions afford students opportunities to develop their metalinguistic awareness and their ability to self-regulate learning, as students come to reflect on and internalize AI-based feedback on their language (Duncanson, 2024). From a sociocultural perspective, writing pedagogy shifts the conventional discourse of writing as a solitary act to one that is socially and technologically enabled. Authoring with AI is not considered to be operating in isolation from other learners, but rather as a social process of negotiating meaning and receiving ongoing support. This promotes not only writing skills but also learner autonomy, and, in so doing, confidence in language use (Athanasopoulos et al., 2023).

2.2.2. *Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)*

To gain a comprehensive understanding of how and why to perceive and utilize AI tools like ChatGPT in writing development, the TAM (Davis, 1989) provides an important lens. TAM suggests that the two primary constructs, perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use, influence users' acceptance and continued use of technology. These beliefs play a significant role in language learners' motivation, engagement, and ultimate success, particularly in educational contexts such as second- or foreign-language learning. Perceived usefulness indicates how much a learner believes that using an AI tool would improve their writing performance. In the EFL learning environment, this may result in measurable enhancements in fluency, grammatical accuracy, vocabulary size, and writing confidence (Rusmiyanto et al., 2023). For example, if students see concrete benefits (e.g., more organization, fewer grammar errors) from using the tool, they are more likely to view it as a valuable part of their learning. This positive attitude then promotes greater engagement with writing and a greater preparedness to rethink and revise, both of which are key components of effective writing.

On the other hand, perceived ease of use refers to how easy learners find the technology they are using. Tools such as ChatGPT can also help lower technical barriers by providing an intuitive, natural-language interface that can be used by those with limited digital literacy or prior experience with other academic writing tools (Woo et al., 2023). The ability to interact in this way helps reduce writing anxiety and enables learners to tackle complex writing tasks with greater confidence. Particularly in EFL contexts, where learners may not be exposed to academic discourse and are not well prepared for writing, these user-friendly features of the tools can make the writing environment more holistic and supportive (Zou et al., 2024).

The integration of TAM with SCT, along with writing and AI affordances, provides a comprehensive model for examining how students engage with AI-scaffolded writing. At the same time, SCT emphasizes AI as a mediating tool that operates within learners' ZPD. In contrast, TAM highlights students' attitudes and behavioral intentions. Attitudes are important because effective technology pedagogy may not matter if learners never accept or adopt it. Considering these theories collectively, we can gain a comprehensive insight into how AI tools, exemplified by ChatGPT, serve not only as technological tools but also as pedagogical partners in shaping the cognitive, social, and affective dimensions of language learning. Thus, it is essential for educators who use AI tools effectively and equitably in EFL

writing instruction to understand students' perceptions of their usefulness and usability. Such findings could inform professional development, instructional design, and curriculum implementation practices, enabling AI to facilitate rather than impede language learning.

2.3. ChatGPT in EFL Writing Instruction

ChatGPT, a product of OpenAI, is a powerful language-based model that uses machine learning to produce human-like text. It is a writing tool suitable for EFL learners, but it goes well beyond pure writing instruction, helping them with many key aspects of the writing process. Adapting ChatGPT can provide a tool that meets the specific needs of EFL learners, ranging from idea generation to drafting support, and including grammatical corrections and vocabulary improvement (Alzahrani & Alotaibi, 2024). The flexibility of ChatGPT encourages adaptive learning, enhances engagement, and increases writing skills in foreign language learning (Pokrivčáková, 2019).

2.3.1. ChatGPT as a writing assistant

ChatGPT, an artificial intelligence generative engine created by OpenAI, is powered by large language models that utilize datasets from various genres and domains. It produces fluent, contextually coherent, and grammatical text (OpenAI, 2023). By creating multiple versions of a paragraph, ChatGPT also increases exposure to lexical and syntactic patterns, which can be thought to promote linguistic diversity in student writing. This corresponds to process writing models that focus on drafting and redrafting. Alshehri (2024) and Nazari et al. (2021) highlight the role of ChatGPT in making writing easier for learners, thereby increasing their confidence and encouraging them to experiment with their writing. Moreover, Muslimin et al. (2024) posit that ChatGPT can make a writing prompt more student-friendly and humane by fostering an engaging, supportive writing environment.

2.3.2. ChatGPT as a feedback provider

Outside of drafting, ChatGPT acts as a real-time suggestions checker. It offers functions for grammar correction, sentence reconstruction, and vocabulary suggestions, helping EFL learners improve their fluency. In contrast to conventional grammar checkers, ChatGPT provides explanations in conversational style and revises feedback upon request, thereby promoting more autonomous language learning. Previous studies demonstrate the profound impact of AI-based feedback on writing quality and language skills (Al-Raimi et al., 2024; Fitria, 2022). With ChatGPT providing immediate feedback, students can make independent revisions, thereby developing self-regulation and metacognitive awareness (Mudawy & Mohammed, 2024). Its lexical recommendations, Mun (2024) adds, reinforce language learning by extending the learner's lexical repertoire and expressive scope.

2.3.3. ChatGPT as a genre and style model

In addition to assisting with grammar and content, ChatGPT also serves as a genre model. Learners can use it to produce texts across multiple genres, such as essays, reports, narratives, and formal emails, in ways that suit particular tones, structures, and communicative purposes. This model helps students absorb traits of various genres and learn about audience expectations (Hyland, 2007). Cheng and Zhang (2022) indicated that learners can discover narrative art, persuasive strategies, and stylistic art by learning diverse genre examples through ChatGPT. Moussa and Belhiah (2024) note that this exposure contributes to genre awareness and rhetorical flexibility, which are key to academic writing proficiency. In general, ChatGPT is a disruptive instrument for EFL writing courses. Being a multitasker, it lends itself to idea-jotting, drafting, revising, and genre work. When used judiciously, integrated into pedagogical practice, it promotes learner engagement, autonomy, and writing ability. To

fully benefit from its educational potential, educators should pair ChatGPT with explicit instruction, critical reflection assignments, and guidelines for ethical use, thereby enabling students to engage strategically and responsibly with AI when writing in class.

2.4. Learners' Perceptions of Using ChatGPT in Writing

2.4.1. Motivations for using ChatGPT tools among EFL learners

The increased concern among EFL writers about using ChatGPT centered on the belief that it would improve writing efficiency and fluency. ChatGPT is cherished for its ability to generate ideas, rephrase vague sentences, and overcome writer's block. Its natural language generation functions can also prompt students to experiment with a variety of vocabulary and sentence structures, which may be important for studying more advanced forms of writing, such as persuasive essays and reports (Wang, 2025). Furthermore, the conversational interface emulates a human conversation, allowing feedback and clarification to be provided with ease. These elements align with students' larger objectives of enhancing academic achievement, gaining confidence, and pursuing self-regulated learning in writing, as outlined in the functionalist theory of motivation (Zhang, 2024).

However, another important factor is the need for immediate assistance. ChatGPT facilitates real-time comments and suggestions, allowing students to instantly revise their writing rather than waiting for teacher feedback, an option valued primarily among students with anxiety during the writing process, particularly in offline settings (Baek et al., 2023; Song & Song, 2023). The tool's capacity to tailor interactions with personalized questions supports learner autonomy and motivation (Syahrin & Akmal, 2024). Learners are further drawn to ChatGPT's ability to adapt to a wide range of writing styles, genres, and topics. This broader exposure prompts exploration of various formats and tones and develops learners' knowledge of successful academic and creative writing practices (Boudouaia et al., 2024).

2.4.2. Perceived benefits of ChatGPT in writing skills

Across diverse EFL contexts, research indicates that students generally perceive ChatGPT as a supportive cognitive tool in English writing. Learners report that it enhances the writing process by facilitating idea generation, improving text organization, and providing immediate feedback on grammar, vocabulary, and coherence, thereby increasing drafting efficiency and revision effectiveness (Alqahtani, 2024; Bok & Cho, 2023; Cabuquin et al., 2024; Jarrah et al., 2023). There are also notable benefits, including improved writing quality in organization, coherence, and fluency, when learners receive structured, constructive feedback, as the tool offers (Mun, 2024; Song & Song, 2023). ChatGPT support has helped build students' confidence in taking on more fundamentally challenging writing tasks at the same level, without fear of being penalized for errors (Mun, 2024; Nguyen, 2023). Moreover, the instant feedback feature of ChatGPT would serve as a motivator to maintain learners' concentration and effort in writing the feedback; as such, learners will practice and actively engage with the language (Alsofyani & Barzanji, 2024; Baek et al., 2023).

2.4.3. Perceived challenges and limitations of ChatGPT in writing skills

Along with these benefits, EFL students identify various issues and limitations in using ChatGPT. One concern is excessive dependence that may lead to a diminished sense of learner autonomy. Some learners rely on AI-generated suggestions, weakening their critical thinking and reducing their likelihood of engaging in cognitive challenges, problem-solving, and language awareness (Mun, 2024; Teng, 2024). Another frequent complaint is the lack of confidence in the obtained output. It can generate grammatically correct sentences many times; however, learners report instances in which the generated sentences are contextually

irrelevant, factually incorrect, or culturally inappropriate (Alsofyani & Barzanji, 2024). This may confuse or discourage the complete acceptance of the tool in academic writing.

The morality of the situation is also well reflected in students' views. Some students are concerned about the possibility of plagiarism and the validity of their work when relying heavily on AI (Matsubara, 2024). These concerns highlight the need for more transparent academic policies and user training to promote the ethical, critical, and informed use of AI in second-language learning. One primary concern is the risk of overreliance on AI, which may hinder the development of independent writing skills and foster passive learning habits (Teng, 2024). Additionally, learners sometimes encounter ambiguous or task-irrelevant feedback, especially in complex writing contexts, making it difficult for them to interpret or trust the AI's suggestions. This can lead to confusion and reduced engagement with the revision process. Furthermore, the issue of academic honesty remains a critical concern, as the boundary between acceptable support and unethical assistance remains unclear, fueling ongoing debates about the ethical use of AI in educational settings.

3. Method

3.1. Research Design

The current study is a mixed-methods investigation of EFL learners' perceptions of using ChatGPT as a writing support tool. Quantitative data were given primary priority, followed by qualitative data to further explain the results. In the initial phase, the structured questionnaire is designed to collect quantitative data on learners' motivation, perceived benefits, and perceived challenges related to using ChatGPT for writing. In the second phase, semi-structured interviews were conducted with a subsample of participants to provide deeper insights into learners' writing experiences, attitudes, and reflections on their use of ChatGPT. Qualitative data are collected through semi-structured interviews with a subsample of participants.

3.2. Participants

This study included 258 English majors from universities in southern Vietnam. These were students in different, writing-intensive courses. A convenience sampling approach was utilized. Initially, the researchers approached the lecturers teaching academic writing courses for their permission to invite students in these classes to participate in this study. An invitation outlining the study's purpose, procedures, and voluntary nature was then distributed to students either in class or via institutional online platforms. To qualify, students had to have taken at least one semester of academic English writing and be familiar with using ChatGPT writing tools.

Table 1.

Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Demographic variable	Category	Number	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	182	70.5
	Female	76	29.5
Age	18-19 years	82	31.8
	20-21 years	78	30.2
	Over 21 years	98	38.0
English proficiency	A2 (Basic Users)	142	55.0
	B1 (Intermediate Users)	96	37.2
	B2 (Upper-Intermediate Users)	20	7.8
Familiarity with ChatGPT	Less than 3 months	41	15.9
	3-6 months	112	43.4
	More than 6 months	105	40.7

3.3. Instruments

A structured questionnaire was employed in the current investigation to examine EFL learners' perceptions of their application of ChatGPT in English writing, specifically regarding the motivations for using ChatGPT, its benefits, and the challenges it might pose to writing skills. The 30-item questionnaire included 10 items per cluster and was rated on a 5-point Likert scale from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree).

The first cluster explores learners' perceptions of why they used ChatGPT, including instant feedback, generating ideas, tailored feedback, alleviating writing anxiety, and prioritizing goal-oriented writing instruction (Alqahtani, 2024; Mun, 2024; Song & Song, 2023). The second cluster reflects respondents' perceptions of the benefits they gained, including heightened vocabulary, grammatical accuracy, organization, coherence, and personal confidence in writing (Bok & Cho, 2023; Cabuquin et al., 2024; Jarrah et al., 2023). The third one uncovers perceived challenges, including overdependence, a lack of critical thinking, distrust in the authenticity and ethics of content, and confusion (Alsofyani & Barzanji, 2024; Matsubara, 2024; Teng, 2024).

The items were developed based on a comprehensive review of current literature and underwent expert validation for content relevance and clarity. A pilot test with a small group of students confirmed internal consistency, with Cronbach's alpha values for all three clusters exceeding 0.80. The questionnaire data provided a quantitative foundation for identifying learner perceptions and patterns of ChatGPT use in writing contexts. Additionally, semi-structured interviews with 20 participants provide qualitative insights into learners' experiences, and responses are analyzed thematically to uncover recurring themes and perceptions. Meanwhile, questionnaire data are quantitatively analyzed in SPSS to identify patterns of adaptation and usage, providing a comprehensive understanding of how EFL learners engage with ChatGPT in their writing practices.

Table 2.

Description of the Questionnaire

Clusters	No. of items	Sample	Source
Motivations for using ChatGPT	10	I use ChatGPT because it is available anytime I need help.	Song & Song, 2023
Benefits	10	ChatGPT helps me write more grammatically accurate sentences.	Bok & Cho, 2023
Challenges	10	I sometimes find it difficult to trust ChatGPT's suggestions.	Teng, 2024

Note. The table does not include all items. Instead, only one item from each cluster is presented as a reference.

3.4. Data Collection

This study used a questionnaire and semi-structured interviews to investigate EFL learners' beliefs about the use of ChatGPT in English writing. A survey on the motivations, benefits, and challenges of ChatGPT use was conducted among 258 university students in the Mekong Delta. It took them approximately 25–30 minutes to complete the questionnaire, which was either printed in the classroom or accessed online via a Google Form. All answers were given on a 5-point Likert scale, with 1 (Strongly Disagree) at one end and 5 (Strongly Agree) at the other. To ensure the instrument's reliability and clarity, the questionnaire was piloted with a small sample of students, and a few changes were made based on their feedback. In addition to the survey, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 20 respondents to gain a

deeper understanding of their personal experiences with using ChatGPT for writing. Interviews were conducted in person or via Zoom, and all were audio-recorded, transcribed, and thematically analyzed.

3.5. Data Analysis

In the quantitative phase, the questionnaire data were analyzed in SPSS to produce descriptive statistics (means and SDs, frequency counts, among others). The author used descriptive statistics to summarise students' perceptions of their motivations, benefits, and challenges when using ChatGPT for writing. In the second phase, semi-structured interviews with 20 participants were transcribed verbatim and analyzed using thematic analysis. An inductive coding approach was employed to identify recurring themes and subthemes related to students' motivations for using ChatGPT, perceived benefits in EFL writing, and perceived challenges, including concerns about overreliance and ethical implications.

4. Findings

4.1. Quantitative Results

4.1.1. Motivations for using ChatGPT in EFL writing

Table 3 presents the descriptive statistics for ten items related to EFL learners' motivations for using ChatGPT in writing. Overall, the results indicate a strong motivation among students to engage with the tool, as all mean scores exceed 4.00 on a 5-point Likert scale.

Table 3.

Descriptive Statistics for Motivations for Using ChatGPT in EFL Writing

Statements	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
1. I use ChatGPT to improve my writing fluency.	258	4.18	.78
2. I use ChatGPT because it is available anytime I need help.	258	4.41	.65
3. ChatGPT motivates me to write without teacher supervision.	258	4.05	.84
4. I use ChatGPT to overcome writer's block.	258	4.10	.81
5. I am motivated by the instant responses ChatGPT provides.	258	4.33	.69
6. ChatGPT encourages me to experiment with new vocabulary and sentence structures.	258	4.21	.73
7. I use ChatGPT to explore different writing styles and tones.	258	4.07	.76
8. ChatGPT increases my confidence in academic writing.	258	4.15	.77
9. ChatGPT supports my self-directed learning goals.	258	4.22	.72
10. I use ChatGPT when I feel anxious about writing assignments.	258	4.02	.88

The most prominent reason appears to be that ChatGPT is available 24/7 ($M = 4.41$, $SD = 0.65$). This indicates that learners appreciate the anytime, anywhere availability of writing assistance, free of classroom time or teacher schedules. A lower standard deviation also implies greater consistency among the sample. This result reflects the growing importance of the flexibility and independence AI tools offer for self-directed learning in digital pedagogy. Nearly as high is the inspiration that comes from ChatGPT's instant feedback feature ($M = 4.33$, $SD = 0.69$), which presumably satisfies learners' demand for swift responses, particularly in high-stakes or tight academic writing contexts. Immediate feedback reduces the cognitive burden of waiting for teacher-provided feedback and allows learners to proceed with the writing process with confidence.

Learners also expressed strong motivation to use ChatGPT to improve writing fluency ($M = 4.18$, $SD = 0.78$), build confidence in academic writing ($M = 4.15$, $SD = 0.77$), and explore

new vocabulary and sentence patterns ($M = 4.21$, $SD = 0.73$). Furthermore, these artifacts may represent a more profound pedagogical value: students not only use AI in a “get them to do the job” mode but also aim for linguistic variety and style, thereby demonstrating “proactive learning”. That level of engagement suggests that ChatGPT is not just a writing assistant but also a learning companion. Furthermore, learners acknowledged that ChatGPT is beneficial for achieving self-study goals ($M = 4.22$, $SD = 0.72$) and for writing with less teacher support ($M = 4.05$, $SD = 0.84$). These findings are crucial, as they indicate a shift towards learner agency, encouraging students to take more control over their learning. The use of ChatGPT as a motivational scaffold also suggests gains in learner autonomy as a key tenet of learner-centered language teaching. Another significant motivator was relief from writer’s block ($M = 4.10$, $SD = 0.81$), indicating that students use ChatGPT to generate initial thoughts, rephrase materials, or brainstorm topics, which can cause anxiety and hinder writing production. Paradoxically, the item with the lowest mean was “I use ChatGPT when I feel anxious about writing assignments” ($M = 4.02$, $SD = 0.88$). It suggests that learners have different perspectives. For some, ChatGPT is very obviously a method of managing writing anxiety. Still, I suspect others are resistant to it as an aid to emotional or psychological support for a variety of reasons (legitimacy, responsibility, safety, codependence, etc.).

4.1.2. Perceived benefits of ChatGPT in writing skills

Table 4 presents descriptive results on learners’ perceptions of ChatGPT’s benefits for improving English writing skills.

Table 4.

Descriptive Statistics: Perceived Benefits of ChatGPT in Writing Skills

Statements	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
11. ChatGPT helps expand my vocabulary.	258	4.35	.63
12. ChatGPT provides useful synonyms and paraphrasing.	258	4.38	.60
13. ChatGPT helps me write more grammatically accurate sentences.	258	4.26	.67
14. I learn sentence structure and syntax from ChatGPT’s suggestions.	258	4.19	.68
15. ChatGPT improves the organization of my writing.	258	4.14	.72
16. I can maintain coherence in essays better with ChatGPT.	258	4.11	.70
17. ChatGPT gives me helpful feedback without judgment.	258	4.24	.65
18. I feel less anxious about writing after using ChatGPT.	258	4.10	.78
19. ChatGPT encourages me to take on more challenging writing tasks.	258	4.06	.75
20. Instant feedback from ChatGPT keeps me focused and engaged.	258	4.17	.71

The highest-rated benefit was that ChatGPT offers useful synonyms and paraphrasing ($M = 4.38$, $SD = 0.60$). This result indicates that students often use the tool as a lexico-grammatical resource to enhance lexical variety and avoid repetition in academic writing, a crucial dimension of stylistic growth. Students also reported that using ChatGPT broadens their vocabulary ($M = 4.35$, $SD = 0.63$), suggesting its contribution to lexical enrichment, particularly for those striving to increase the complexity and sophistication of their written English. Another major aid, according to the respondents, is ChatGPT’s grammar skills, with a mean score of 4.26 on the item “ChatGPT helps me write more grammatically accurate sentences.” Additionally, the low standard deviation suggests little controversy, allowing students to recognize that ChatGPT serves as a valuable source of corrective feedback. Relatedly, they agreed that ChatGPT reinforces their knowledge of sentence structure and syntax ($M = 4.19$), suggesting that students could learn and adopt grammatical rules through iterative interaction with the tool’s output.

In addition to enhancing the sentence-level fluency, participants also described that ChatGPT maintains text-level organization and coherence. Remarkably, prompts addressing the organization of writing ($M = 4.14$) and the coherence of the essay ($M = 4.11$) suggest that students perceive ChatGPT as challenging to organize logical arguments and link ideas cohesively. This is moving from AI being used for micro adjustments and micro corrections to AI as your macro-level writing assistant. ChatGPT is particularly valued by participants for not judging their participation ($M = 4.24$), suggesting that the AI's non-threatening behavior may help lower writing apprehension and promote structure in writing productions. This is reflected in the finding that, after using the tool, learners are less anxious about writing ($M = 4.10$, $SD = 0.78$). In the present findings, the higher SD might represent different levels of anxiety in students, such that although these students felt generally satisfied, some students may experience greater emotional benefits than others. Lastly, students perceived some motivational benefits from ChatGPT, as it made them more willing to undertake harder writing tasks ($M = 4.06$) and helped them stay focused and engaged through instant feedback ($M = 4.17$). These findings suggest that ChatGPT not only improves cognitive and language development but also emotional engagement, both of which are crucial for successful writing practice.

4.1.3. Perceived challenges of ChatGPT in writing skills

Table 5 presents students' perceptions of the challenges of using ChatGPT for writing. The data reveal a consistent pattern of concern, with all mean scores above 3.60, indicating a moderate to high level of awareness among learners of ChatGPT's limitations in the EFL writing context.

Table 5.

Descriptive Statistics: Perceived Challenges of ChatGPT in Writing Skills

Statements	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
21. I sometimes rely too much on ChatGPT and become less independent.	258	3.92	.77
22. ChatGPT discourages me from thinking critically about my writing.	258	3.68	.85
23. I have seen ChatGPT generate factually incorrect information.	258	3.87	.81
24. ChatGPT sometimes produces contextually inappropriate content.	258	3.74	.79
25. I worry about plagiarism when I use ChatGPT.	258	3.83	.84
26. I'm unsure if using ChatGPT violates academic honesty.	258	3.95	.82
27. Feedback from ChatGPT can be vague or irrelevant.	258	3.69	.76
28. I sometimes find it difficult to trust ChatGPT's suggestions.	258	3.64	.80
29. I am unclear about the ethical use of ChatGPT in writing.	258	3.98	.78
30. Using ChatGPT might hinder the development of my writing skills.	258	3.91	.79

The highest mean score has been assigned to “I am unclear about the ethical use of ChatGPT in writing” ($M = 3.98$, $SD = 0.78$) item, followed by “I'm unsure if using ChatGPT violates academic honesty” ($M = 3.95$, $SD = 0.82$). These figures reveal high levels of uncertainty among students regarding the ethical permissibility of AI use in the academic environment. This result underscores the need for institutional guidance and transparent policies for AI tools in writing instruction.

Another prominent concern is overdependence. For example, “I sometimes rely too much on ChatGPT and become less independent” scored 3.92, and “Using ChatGPT might hinder the development of my writing skills” got 3.91. It seems that students value the help as support from the tool. Still, many are aware that excessive reliance on AI could undermine their long-term language development and autonomy as learners. There were also issues of accuracy and relevance. Many users mentioned that “ChatGPT generates factually incorrect

information" (M = 3.87) and "produces contextually inappropriate content" (M = 3.74). Additionally, learners reported that "Feedback from ChatGPT can be vague or irrelevant" (M = 3.69) and that "difficult to trust ChatGPT's suggestions can be difficult to trust" (M = 3.64). These concerns raise questions about the tool's reliability, particularly for nuanced writing or situation-specific assignments.

Moreover, issues of cognitive development were raised in "ChatGPT discourages me to think critically about the writing" (M = 3.68), which indicates concern that ChatGPT might hinder learners' involvement in the writing process by providing ready-made answers rather than encouraging active problematization. There is also an issue with plagiarism and authenticity. The statement "I worry about plagiarism when I use ChatGPT" received a response of 3.83, indicating that a significant portion of students are unsure whether ChatGPT-generated content can be ethically incorporated into their academic work. This is closely related to the more general uncertainty surrounding academic integrity and institutional rules.

4.2. Qualitative Results

4.2.1. Motivations for using ChatGPT in EFL writing

This student emphasizes the emotional threshold of anxiety, which is a typical issue in EFL writing in connection with/because of fear of making mistakes in grammar, vocabulary, and organization. Getting started may be easier with ChatGPT, which provides example text, such as an introduction, thereby reducing the steep learning curve of creating something novel from scratch. This student shared,

I usually feel nervous when I start writing tasks because I'm afraid of making mistakes. ChatGPT helps me begin with something. Even just seeing a sample introduction motivates me to try, and I end up writing more than I expected. It removes that initial fear I always have. (Participant 1)

This quote highlights that, for EFL students who may be insecure about their language abilities, ChatGPT must foster a judgment-free zone. Without judgment, it is easier for the novice to explore, to ask questions from the expert's perspective that may seem naive, and to identify incorrect approaches without fear of rebuke. This gain in confidence leads to more practice in writing, in and out of academic contexts. "I never felt that before" captures the transformative nature of ChatGPT, suggesting it inspires a new level of excitement for writing that did not exist before.

What motivates me most about using ChatGPT is that it doesn't judge. I can make grammar mistakes or ask simple questions without feeling embarrassed. That makes me more confident and pushes me to keep writing more frequently, even outside class. I never felt that before with writing activities. (Participant 3)

This student highlights the practicality of 24/7 access to ChatGPT conversations, which facilitates self-motivated learning. The expressions "motivate me to finish my writing without delay" point to the immediacy of task completion, and "practice more on my own" points to the immediacy of task completion and enhanced autonomy in learning, respectively. This suggests that ChatGPT empowers students to take more control over their writing practice and enhances their independence as learners. One learner described,

Sometimes I write late at night when my teachers or friends are not available. Knowing ChatGPT is always there motivates me to finish my writing without delay. I can ask for help anytime, and that kind of support really encourages me to practice more on my own. (Participant 5)

In addition, this quote speaks to ChatGPT's potential to help break through writer's block, a common barrier to writing. Quick feedback keeps students from getting stuck creatively, frustrated, or quitting their projects. "Motivates me to go back to my work" captures how ChatGPT sustains engagement, while "changes how I feel about writing tasks completely" conveys a fundamental transformation in the student's relationship to writing.

Whenever I face writer's block or don't know how to continue a paragraph, I turn to ChatGPT. It gives me ideas quickly, which motivates me to keep working instead of giving up. Having that kind of tool completely changes how I feel about writing tasks. (Participant 6)

Every quote highlights a different aspect of ChatGPT's impact, ranging from emotional support to concise solutions. The tool's non-judgmental nature and ever-accessible framework foster an environment of support for experimentation and autonomy, and rapid ideation helps students stay in a state of flow.

4.2.2. Perceived benefits of ChatGPT in EFL writing

This learner notes that ChatGPT has helped them improve sentence structure and word choice, which undoubtedly translates to more effective writing. The tool's prompts cause its students to reflect on how else they could say things. The sentence "I've gradually learned to organize my thoughts more clearly over time" implies a positive impact of learning, which could be interpreted as positive transfer when using ChatGPT. Another benefit of feeling more confident in class is that strong writing skills lead to greater self-assurance in other academic work.

ChatGPT helps me improve my writing by showing me better ways to structure sentences and use advanced vocabulary. After I see its suggestions, I reflect on how I could write differently. Over time, I've learned to organize my ideas more clearly, and my confidence in writing has definitely increased. (Participant 9)

This quote highlights the benefit of ChatGPT's instant feedback, enabling students to see right away where they can improve. "It helps me stay focused and engaged, especially when I am working alone." The speed of response keeps the student engaged, but independent work can lead to feelings of isolation. This lack of frustration and higher productivity imply that instant feedback makes the writing process more interactive and rewarding, making it worthwhile to pursue.

The best part about ChatGPT is that it gives instant feedback. I can copy my draft, ask for suggestions, and within seconds, I know what to improve. It helps me stay focused and engaged, especially when I'm working alone. That immediate response makes writing less frustrating and more productive. (Participant 11)

This student emphasizes ChatGPT's contribution to autonomy by allowing self-directed revision. The tool's capacities in grammar, transitions, and coherence alleviate the need for teacher feedback, as demonstrated by "now I can revise on my own" and "helps me understand what good academic writing should actually look like," suggesting that ChatGPT is used as an educational device that inculcates the conventions of academic writing.

Before using ChatGPT, I always waited for my teacher's feedback. Now I can revise on my own. It corrects grammar, suggests transitions, and even helps with coherence. This makes me feel more independent as a writer and helps me understand what good academic writing should actually look like. (Participant 15)

This quote is about ChatGPT's part in expanding your vocabulary, especially for academic purposes. In addition to providing paraphrased sentences, the tool then "feeds back" the new material to the student's learning, allowing them to develop a sense of correct grammar and alternative ways of expressing the same information. The slogan "It's like learning a new language through real writing practice" signals and endorses ChatGPT's pedagogy: practical, context-driven learning in which students can learn and use new vocabulary in real-world writing.

Using ChatGPT has taught me a lot about academic vocabulary. Sometimes I ask it to paraphrase my sentences, and I learn new ways to express the same idea more formally. I also use those phrases in future assignments. It's like learning new language skills through real writing practice. (Participant 20)

These benefits cover both the technical and emotional aspects of writing. ChatGPT makes recommendations to improve sentence structure, logical flow, and writing formality, and offers real-time feedback that helps students stay engaged and achieve results. Supporting self-directed revision and familiarizing students with conventions, it facilitates autonomy and understanding of writing conventions.

4.2.3. Perceived Challenges of ChatGPT in EFL Writing

This student risks becoming overly dependent on ChatGPT, hindering their ability to think critically and develop independence. "Stop thinking about how I can do better just on my own," explains that a learner does not laugh at the use of equipment, which appears to be a trend towards passivity in writers, a tendency whereby the convenience of doing so becomes more important than the necessity, which is a driver to do so. Moreover, the possibility of "copying of its suggestions" without verifying their correctness or suitability may lead to a lower degree of ownership of the writing process, which can counteract learning and affect learning outcomes in EFL.

One challenge I've noticed is that I rely too much on ChatGPT. When I use it too often, I stop thinking about how to improve myself. I copied its suggestions and forgot to check whether they're correct or even suitable for the assignment I'm working on. (Participant 6)

This statement exposes the ethical gray area surrounding ChatGPT in academia. The confusion over what constitutes acceptable student use, alongside differing teacher attitudes, creates uncertainty that increases stress, particularly over high-stakes tasks. The concern that "I'm scared it might be seen as plagiarism" reflects the absence of clearly defined institutional guidelines, which may, in turn, dissuade students from using ChatGPT as an appropriate educational resource, despite their desire to do so.

Sometimes I get confused about whether I'm allowed to use ChatGPT or not. I've heard different opinions from teachers. I want to use it for learning, but I'm scared it might be seen as plagiarism. That uncertainty makes it stressful, especially when I'm working on important writing tasks. (Participant 8)

The participant also raises the concern that ChatGPT may provide misleading information, which is particularly problematic for academic writing, where accuracy is crucial. It highlights the effects of incorrect information, as seen in “the information was wrong,” underscoring the importance of verifying ChatGPT’s outputs. The student’s move toward being “more careful” implies that using the tool itself can be error-prone in the assignment without cross-checking, underscoring the critical use of ChatGPT in EFL writing.

ChatGPT can be helpful, but not always accurate. I once used it to check an idea, only to later find out the information was incorrect. If I hadn't double-checked, I would've included false content in my assignment. So now I'm more careful and don't fully trust its facts. (Participant 12)

This response expresses frustration with ChatGPT’s feedback quality, which is often vague or generic. The student’s exasperation with comments such as “make (it) more clear” or “rephrase for fluency” suggests that the tool often lacks the granularity needed for effective learning, especially for EFL learners who need explicit guidance on what to do. The statement “still as a learner, I need more specific help” highlights the discrepancy between ChatGPT’s feedback and the instructional intervention needed to address specific writing weaknesses productively.

There are times when ChatGPT gives me feedback that feels very general or vague. It says things like 'improve clarity' or 'reword for flow,' but doesn't explain how. As a learner, I still need more detailed help to really understand what I'm doing wrong and how to fix it. (Participant 17)

Over-reliance may reduce critical thinking, and vague ethical guidelines can cause worry and hesitation. The risk of misinformation necessitates further corroboration (which adds to students’ teaching load), and general feedback does not provide the detailed guidance that EFL students often require. These challenges underscore that, while ChatGPT is a potentially valuable resource, its constraints necessitate careful oversight in both research ethics and academic writing.

5. Discussion

The combined findings from both quantitative and qualitative data suggest that EFL writers have a high level of motivation to incorporate ChatGPT into their writing processes, mainly due to its ease of access (24/7 availability), quick feedback (immediacy), and ease of use (user-friendliness). Learners appreciated the tool’s immediate, non-judgmental feedback, which they said helped reduce their writing anxiety and motivated them to approach independent writing tasks more deeply. The motivation to do so is informed by prior findings (Mun, 2024; Song & Song, 2023), which emphasize ChatGPT’s role in promoting autonomy and fostering learners’ confidence, particularly when teacher support is limited. Moreover, a significant number of students reported that ChatGPT was assisting them with writer’s block, structuring ideas, and expressing themselves more effectively, especially when working on more complex or challenging writing tasks. This finding is consistent with Bok and Cho (2023) and Cabuquin et al. (2024), who have highlighted the tool’s usefulness for promoting self-regulated learning and sustaining long-lasting writing motivation.

From the TAM perspective, these positive perceptions indicate high perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use, two major determinants of learners’ behavioral intention to adopt the tool. In addition, as interpreted through SCT, learners’ engagement with ChatGPT could be considered participation in a tool-mediated activity, in which AI functions as a scaffold that enables writing performance within learners’ ZPD.

These perceptions were substantiated by quantitative data showing that students felt they had significant advantages in correcting grammar, enriching vocabulary, and improving the organization of written texts. These findings align with Alqahtani (2024), who has emphasized AI's role in enhancing learners' linguistic accuracy and promoting more coherent, fluent writing. Learners particularly valued that ChatGPT offered rewording options and expanded their lexical resources, which, in turn, promoted both clarity and stylistic diversity in their academic writing. Notably, some students reported that ChatGPT enabled them to write longer, more complex, and more confident texts and to tackle challenges they would not have otherwise addressed (Baek et al., 2023; Mun, 2024).

The study, however, raised concerns about the tool's use. The fear of becoming overly dependent on ChatGPT was a frequently cited concern, and many worried that it might hinder critical thinking, creativity, and independent writing. These cautions echo those of Teng (2024), who warned that an overreliance on AI-driven tools undermines students' long-term writing development. These limitations decreased learners' trust in the tool and even led to distractions rather than providing clear guidance on what needed to be revised.

From an SCT perspective, excessive reliance could disrupt the gradual withdrawal of scaffolding, which is crucial to independent development beyond the ZPD. The mediational process may not result in authentic internalization if learners access and utilize AI-generated responses to impose on learners rather than as a point for self-reflection. Such concerns may reflect attitudes towards the tool, which, from a TAM standpoint, could decrease sustained behavioral intention to use it.

Ethical issues arose as a second key theme. It was not clear to many students what the parameters were for when and how they should typically seek help with AI, especially regarding questions of plagiarism, originality, and academic integrity. These concerns align with conversations documented by Alsofyani and Barzanji (2024) and Matsubara (2024), which continue to question the role of AI in writing instruction and the need for clearer institutional policy. Some respondents expressed concern that individuals using ChatGPT without training could inadvertently encourage cheating, particularly in formal writing assessments or other assignments that require originality.

Such findings further underscore the relationship between pedagogical mediation and technological acceptance. Although SCT presents AI as an opportunity for culturally productive work, its pedagogical quality depends on guided facilitation that promotes meaningful engagement rather than mindless reliance. Similarly, the TAM proposes that individual perceptions of institutional clarity and ethical guidelines may inform learners' understanding of what is appropriate and legitimate, thereby impacting their disposition to integrate AI responsibly into their writing practices.

6. Conclusion

The purpose of this study was to investigate EFL students' attitudes toward using ChatGPT for English writing practices, based on both quantitative and qualitative data. Results indicate that learners are attracted to three aspects of ChatGPT: 24/7 service, instant responses, and ease of use. These aspects combined to make the learner feel more confident, less anxious about writing, and more involved in the independent writing tasks. Students found grammar correction, vocabulary building, and writing organization helpful. ChatGPT was found to be particularly useful for providing paraphrased responses and facilitating clear, smooth communication of ideas. These advantages motivated students to take on more difficult tasks

and facilitated their self-regulation. However, concerns about overreliance on AI, the erosion of critical thinking skills, and the moral implications of using ChatGPT have surfaced. Some participants also questioned whether the feedback provided was contextually accurate. These difficulties underscore the importance of guided and critical use of AI in language education.

To sum up, ChatGPT has significant potential to improve EFL writing development, but its effectiveness depends on its applicability. Prior to this, teachers should provide clear instructions on ethical use, foster active engagement with feedback, and support students in seeing AI as a tool rather than a substitute for their own writing. With such pedagogical encouragement, ChatGPT could be a rich resource for advancing linguistic competence and writing agency.

Ethical Statement

The author confirmed that the study does not require ethics committee approval under the research integrity rules in his country. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to data collection to ensure confidentiality and anonymity. Participants were fully informed of the study's purpose and their right to withdraw from participation at any time without penalty. (Date of Confirmation: 09/04/2025).

Conflict of Interest

The author declares no conflict of interest.

Data Availability

The data presented in this study are not publicly available due to confidentiality concerns. However, they may be obtained from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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